

GEO.INFORMED

GEO.INFORMED report

Optimization of Reference Data for Deep Learning and Machine Learning Models

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Introduction to the report

The GEO.INFORMED project combined the use of freely available satellite data from the EU's Copernicus program with the application of machine learning and deep learning methods to derive geodata in support of environmental policy in Flanders. More information about the project and its outputs can be found on the project website¹ and on Zenodo².

Deep learning is a state-of-the-art branch of data-driven models that revolves around the use of deep artificial neural networks. While artificial neural networks have been around for decades, the mainstream uptake of their deep variant (containing many layers) was driven by a combination of hardware and software improvements: (i) the (more) efficient use of GPUs; (ii) the introduction of ReLU-type activation functions; (iii) the creation of a new regularization technique called dropout; and (iv) the advent of techniques to mitigate the need for huge amounts of reference data for model training (LeCun et al. 2014). In work package 5 of the GEO.INFORMED project, we focused on the latter aspect, i.e., the need for (large amounts of) labeled reference data.

Why are labeled reference data so important for machine learning and especially deep learning models? Generalization is the capacity of a model to make accurate predictions for unseen data. Low generalization is usually caused by so-called overfitting, where the model starts to 'memorize' the training data so as to obtain high accuracy on the training set (Benjani and Ghatee, 2021). Deep learning models are particularly prone to overfitting because of their large number of trainable parameters (Kabkab et al. 2016).

One of the most effective ways to reduce the risk of overfitting and increase a model's generalization capacity is to increase the number of labeled training data. For many applications, however, the collection of reliable and high-quality ground reference labels is cumbersome. This challenge of small training datasets has been recognized as very common in environmental monitoring (Brigato and Iocchi, 2020).

Therefore, in the GEO.INFORMED project, we have explored and implemented a wide range of methods to improve the generalization capacity of the deep learning (and other machine learning) models we applied. These approaches are **model transferability** (section 1), **transfer learning** (section 2), **data augmentation** (section 3), **self-supervised learning** (section 4), and **active learning** (section 5).

In most use cases of the GEO.INFORMED project, time series of satellite images were used as input data. Therefore, the approaches/solutions described in this report might differ from the more standard image classification and segmentation literature. A brief description of all use cases addressed in the GEO.INFORMED project can be consulted in Heremans (2026).

¹ www.geo-informed.be

² https://zenodo.org/communities/geoinformed_fwo

Section 1 - Temporal model transferability

The assessment of (temporal) model transferability was implemented in use case 2 - Forest monitoring and use case 5 - Catch crops.

Intro and research question

The most standard approach in remote sensing involves training and applying a model using labeled samples that were all collected in the same time period (year, season, etc.). However, this approach can lead to a model with a limited transferability or generalization potential. Model transferability indicates how well a (pre-)trained model performs (i.e., produces accurate predictions) on unseen, new data, even if these data originate from different locations or time periods. Here, we focus on temporal model transferability: when a model is transferred in the temporal domain, for example across satellite images that originate from different years. When a model trained in one (source) year is applied to samples from another (target) year, the classification performance is usually negatively impacted (Gray et al., 2021).

For example, when using model predictions to steer field work for catch crops, an accurate classification of the presence of catch crops is required at the beginning of the season. Only labels from previous years are available, and so models are trained on these previous years (source) and applied to another year not included in training (target), thereby requiring temporally transferable models. Recently, this topic has received more attention in the research area of land cover classification, and in particular crop type classification (Ajadi et al., 2021; Cai et al., 2018; Momm et al., 2020; Wijesingha et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2020).

Temporal transferability is also important in other applications such as forest tree species mapping to enhance the effectiveness and utility of remote sensing-based prediction models. Successful temporal transferability is not guaranteed in the context of a forest ecosystem because of interannual variability of spectral reflectance. This variation may be caused by changing acquisition, atmospheric, and environmental conditions. In particular, the interannual changes in weather conditions can cause changes in species-specific tree phenology as tree species can exhibit different growing patterns and timings. It is expected that this variability can alter the association between the satellite-based input features and the target classes from year to year.

The research question for the temporal transferability assessment was twofold:

1. How well do data-driven models maintain their accuracy when applied to a (target) year not included in the training dataset?
2. How can we improve the temporal generalization capacity of data-driven models?

Data

Use case 2: Forest monitoring

Sentinel-2 time series were generated with the openEO Python API, based on the TERRASCOPE_S2_TOC_V2 data collection and preprocessed to time series with regular time intervals. The preprocessing steps included: (1) cloud masking with a kernel process (std dev 1.5, window size 11), (2) aggregation of time series to equidistant intervals (dekadal and monthly frequency), (3) gap filling through linear interpolation, and (4) spatial aggregation over the plot. We produced year-long time series for each year from 2018 to 2022. All available spectral bands from the visible, red-edge, near-infrared and shortwave infrared regions were included (Table 1.1). Additionally, the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was calculated using B08 and B04 (Tucker, 1979).

Table 1.1: Overview of Sentinel-2 spectral bands used in the Forest monitoring use case.

Band name	Resolution (m)	Central wavelength (nm)	Description
B02	10	490	Blue
B03	10	560	Green
B04	10	665	Red
B05	20	705	Red-edge
B06	20	740	Red-edge
B07	20	783	Red-edge
B08	10	842	NIR
B08A	20	865	NIR
B11	20	1610	SWIR
B12	20	2190	SWIR

The labels for model training and evaluations were obtained from the second and third cycle of Flanders' Regional Forest Inventory (RFI), a policy-supporting measurement network coordinated by the Agency for Nature and Forests (ANF) of the Flemish government (ANF, 2023). For each plot, the dominant tree species labels were used, as derived from the species-specific basal area per hectare. A tree species was considered to be dominant if it occupied 80% or more of the total basal area. Only the five most abundant tree species were retained for this study: Scots pine, black pine, common and sessile oak, poplar, and beech.

Use case 5: Catch crops

The ground truth labels for training and evaluation of the winter crop classification models were obtained through field visits. Three data sources were combined: (1) a dataset from the department of Agriculture and Fisheries of the Flemish government (winter years 2016-2021) obtained in the context of monitoring regional catch crop policy compliance, (2) a targeted field campaign from the winter year 2021 and (3) a targeted field campaign from the winter year 2022³. The original fine-class labels were grouped into seven broader categories: three catch crop groups (grass group, leafy group and mixtures) and four other groups (winter cereals, legumes, other crops and bare fields).

The parcel-level cropSAR crop growth service from VITO was used for generating daily time series over the agricultural parcels. CropSAR provides daily time series by applying a deep learning network trained on cloud-free images of both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 to interpolate between the gaps of optical acquisitions, thereby combining optical and radar data (Van Tricht, 2019). Time series ranged from August to April for the winter years 2016 to 2022, where 2016-2021 were used for training (source years) and 2022 for testing the temporal model transferability (target year).

Methods

Use case 2: Forest monitoring

Three algorithms were selected to perform supervised classification of dominant tree species in this study: Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001), Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Mountrakis et al., 2011), and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) (Wang et al., 2017). These algorithms were implemented in Python with the scikit-learn library (version 1.3.2) (Pedregosa et al., 2011). An exhaustive grid search was carried out to determine suitable parameter values for each algorithm. The resulting parameter values are summarized in Table 1.2. All other parameters were kept at their default value.

³ A winter year always spans from August of the indicated year until April the year after

Table 1.2: Chosen parameter values for the Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) algorithms.

	Parameter	Chosen value
RF	n_estimators	500
	max_depth	7
	class_weight	balanced
SVM	kernel	rbf
	C	100
	gamma	0.1
	class_weight	balanced
MLP	hidden_layer_sizes	(100,)
	activation	relu
	solver	adam
	alpha	0.01
	learning_rate	adaptive

The 653 plots from the RFI dataset were split into a training and validation subset by taking a stratified random sample using a 70:30 ratio. Different so-called ‘input scenarios’ were compared to (1) establish baseline model performances, (2) determine the change in accuracy when temporally transferring trained models, and (3) explore the impact of multi-year training data on temporal transferability. First, same-year single-year input scenarios were used to establish reference model performances for each year of satellite data from 2018 to 2022 (Figure 1.1a). Second, the same-year single-year input scenarios were compared to cross-year single-year scenarios to gain insight into and quantify the temporal transferability of trained classification models. For the five available validation years from 2018 to 2022, each hypothetically possible transfer scenario was carried out, resulting in 20 input scenarios (Figure 1.1b). Third, multi-year training data was used to investigate its impact on temporal transferability based on 15 input scenarios (Figure 1.1c). The performance of the classifiers was consistently evaluated on the same set of validation plots using the overall accuracy and class-level F1 scores as evaluation metrics.

Figure 1.1: Overview of the three groups of applied classification approaches: (a) the same-year single-year input scenarios, (b) the cross-year single-year input scenarios, and (c) the cross-year multi-year input scenarios. [Figure from Verhulst et al., 2024]

Use case 5: Catch crops

Three models were compared for the classification of catch crops: Random Forest (RF), Time Series Forest (TSF), and 1-Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN). RF is a widely used algorithm in (crop) classification and it does not take into account the order of the inputs. TSF is an extension of RF that uses temporal aggregates of the original input variables (mean, standard deviation and slope of random intervals) as model inputs (Van Tricht et al., 2018; Yi et al., 2022). The more recent 1D-CNN model has gained popularity in crop classification due to its explicit handling of time series through temporal convolution operations (Pelletier et al., 2019). The architecture of the 1D-CNN model consists of three sequential convolutional blocks, each composed of a one-dimensional convolutional layer, a batch normalization layer, and a ReLU activation function. These were followed by two fully connected blocks, each containing a linear layer, a batch normalization layer, and a ReLU activation function.

These three models were compared using multivariate (NDVI, fAPAR and FCover) time series data with variable time series lengths as input data. These varying lengths were tested to assess the models' early-season classification capabilities. Initially, the models were trained and tested on data from winter years 2016-2021. Subsequently, they were trained on data from 2016-2021 (5921 fields) and validated with time series from 2022 (970 fields), specifically to assess their temporal transferability potential. The classification process of the time series followed a two-level hierarchical approach, first classifying the presence of a winter crop and then classifying the winter crop itself. Based on the classification results, the resulting categories were regrouped into two categories in a post-classification step: catch crops and other. The performance of the models was compared using the binary averaged F1-score as a comprehensive measure for this classification task. An F1-score is calculated by:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{recall}}$$

Where precision is the proportion of positive (negative) predictions that are actually positive (negative) and recall is the proportion of positives (negatives) that are actually predicted as positive (negative).

Results

Use case 2: Forest monitoring

The same-year single-year input scenarios resulted in useful model performance baselines for each validation year and each algorithm (Figure 1.2). First, RF showed a performance between 76.63% ± 0.86 and 80.97% ± 0.68 for the different years. The performance of SVM varied more, with overall accuracy values between 76.02% and 86.22%. Finally, MLP generally performed worse compared to RF and SVM with overall accuracies between 71.94% ± 1.3 and 78.93% ± 1.23.

Figure 1.2: Overall accuracies (OA, %) of the same-year single-year input scenarios for each tested classification algorithm: Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). For RF and MLP, each boxplot represents the range of OA values for the 10 executed repetitions of model training and validation. For SVM, each asterisk represents the resulting OA value, since there is no variance due to random initialization. [Figure from Verhulst et al., 2024].

Temporally transferring a trained classification model resulted in a substantial drop in overall accuracy, ranging from $2.81 \pm 0.77\%$ pt to $8.12 \pm 2.71\%$ pt for RF, from $3.19 \pm 2.65\%$ pt to $14.92 \pm 3.10\%$ pt for SVM, and from $2.30 \pm 5.38\%$ pt to $9.03 \pm 2.74\%$ pt for MLP (Figure 1.3). There are no consistent patterns in species-specific accuracy loss.

Figure 1.3: a) Overall accuracies (OA) (%) for the cross-year single-year input scenarios for the three tested algorithms: Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). For RF and MLP, each boxplot represents the range of OA values for the 10 executed repetitions of model training and validation. For SVM, each asterisk represents the resulting OA value, since there is no variance due to random initialization. For reference, the same-year single-year classifications are added. (b–d) Mean accuracy loss (%pt) per validation year with standard error bars for the cross-year single-year input scenarios compared to the same-year single-year input scenario of the same validation year for (b) RF, (c) SVM, and (d) MLP. [Figure from Verhulst et al., 2024]

The use of multi-year training data substantially reduced the drop in overall accuracy (Figure 1.4). As more years of satellite data were added to the training dataset, the accuracy loss became smaller. In the case of MLP, there was even no accuracy loss, but rather an improvement compared to the scenario with single-year training data.

Figure 1.4: (a) Overall accuracies (OA, %) for the multi-year input scenarios for the three tested algorithms: Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). For RF and MLP, each boxplot represents the range of OA values for the 10 executed repetitions of model training and validation. For SVM, each asterisk represents the resulting OA value, since there is no variance due to random initialization. The same-year single-year classifications are added as baseline reference, along with one of the cross-year single-year scenarios. (b–d) Mean accuracy loss (%pt) per number of included training years with standard error bars for the multi-year input scenarios compared to the same-year single-year input scenario of the corresponding validation year for (b) RF, (c) SVM, and (d) MLP. [Figure adapted from Verhulst et al., 2024].

Use case 5: Catch crops

When training and evaluating on the same years, all models showed an increase in F1-scores when including extra time steps throughout the first three months (September, October, November) (Figure 1.5, top). However, adding extra time steps only marginally improves model performance from December until February, as signaled by a stagnation in the F1-scores. The inclusion of March and April to the time series again resulted in a notable increase of the F1-scores.

When evaluating the early-season performance of the models separately, the forest-based models (RF and TSF) attain a median F1-score surpassing 85% in November, whereas the CNN model only reaches this threshold in March (Figure 1.5, top). By April, all models reach their highest median F1-score. However, the CNN model resulted in lower and more variable F1-scores, particularly earlier in the season.

After applying the trained models to reference parcels from an unseen (winter) year, the increase in F1 scores throughout the growing season remained for the forest-based models (Figure 1.5, bottom). In contrast, the CNN model displayed unstable performance that lacked this general upward trend and was characterized by large variation between individual model runs. For all three models, accuracy peaked in April with median F1-scores of 88.8% for RF, 88.3% for TSF and 81.5% for the CNN model. The forest-based models approached their best median F1-scores from the training years (RF 88.7% and TSF 88.9%) when applied to the unseen test year (88.8% for RF and TSF 88.3%), while the CNN model's median F1-score was markedly lower for the unseen target year (81.5%) than for the training years (87.9%).

Regarding early-season performance in the training years, TSF surpassed the F1-score threshold of 85% in December, RF did so in February, whereas the CNN model stays below this threshold throughout the entire growing season. When applied to the unseen target year, both forest-based models surpass the threshold later in the season than for the training years.

Figure 1.5: Mean F1-scores throughout the growing season for training years (2016-2021, top) and target year (2022, bottom). The shaded area indicates the standard deviation on the mean F1 scores. X-axis shows the end point of the time series: e.g. Dec represents a time series starting in August and ending in December (RF & TSF overlap). 85% Threshold indicated with a dashed red line. [Figure adapted from Vanpoucke et al., 2024].

Conclusions

Use case 2: Forest monitoring

The transferability assessment for this use case showed that Sentinel-2 time series can be effectively used for dominant tree species classification in temperate forests. When going for the traditional “single-year” route, classification performances of 75% and higher were achieved with the RF and SVM algorithms. The MLP algorithm showed less consistent performance. When applying these single-year models to samples from another year, the overall accuracy dropped by 2.30 to 14.92 percentage points. This shows that caution is needed when applying trained models on time periods that were not seen by the model during the training phase. The use of multi-year training data could partially mitigate the

observed drop in overall accuracy. This suggests that the use of labeled training samples that originate from multiple years is preferred to maximize the temporal transferability of our tree species classification models.

Use case 5: Catch crops

When comparing the models for their early-season classification capabilities on the unseen validation year, we see that the forest-based models reach the threshold F1-score of 85% later in the season than for the years included in training. A slight drop in performance on a separate target year is expected, as temporal (and spatial) transferability is generally a challenge in crop classification, even when multiple years have been used for training (Račić et al. 2024). This is due to different weather conditions between years, which affect crop development and result in different temporal profiles for the same crop (Račić et al. 2024; Weilandt et al., 2023).

However, interannual differences do not entirely explain the lack of generalization to the target year for the 1D-CNN model, its results most likely point to an overfitting problem. Given the large number of parameters that need to be fitted for a deep learning model such as a CNN, deep learning models require many labels to be fitted (Ma et al., 2024). For example, both Pelletier et al. (2019) and Zhong et al. (2019) used 1D-CNNs and respectively used about 1 million and 2 million training samples. The limited number of samples (6000) for our catch crop classification could thus be a likely explanation for its limited generalizability. Fortunately, recent research addresses this aspect of limited labeled data availability in a deep learning context. Here, transfer learning, a machine learning technique that transfers knowledge between related tasks, has emerged as a strategy to alleviate the need for labeled data, also in environmental remote sensing (Ma et al., 2024).

Section 2 - Transfer learning

Transfer learning, with multispectral satellite time series as inputs, was implemented in use case 5 - Catch crops.

Intro and research question

The assessment of temporal model transferability in the previous section indicates that the deep learning 1D-CNN model struggled to generalize well to unseen data from an unseen target year. This is most likely due to the limited number of labeled samples available for training (~ 6000 parcels). Deep learning models, which require many parameters to be fitted, need large amounts of ground truth data (Ma et al., 2024).

Transfer learning, a machine learning technique that transfers knowledge between related tasks, has recently emerged as a strategy to reduce the need for extensive labeled data (Ma et al., 2024). For instance, Pandžić et al. (2024) demonstrated the effectiveness of transfer learning for enhancing the transferability of crop mapping models using Sentinel-1 data.

Therefore, in this section we focus on the use of such pretrained models for our catch crop classification task. We will use the Breizhcrops module in Python, which provides pretrained, main crop classification models for Sentinel-2 time series (Rußwurm et al., 2020). The similarity of the training tasks - field-level Sentinel-2 time series-based crop classification - makes this module ideal for its transferability to our classification task. Of course, a domain shift still remains between the classification of summer crops to winter crops. This shift is partially addressed through a fine-tuning step of the pretrained models, where they are presented with and trained on data of the target classification task, in this case catch crop classification.

We explore the feasibility of using these pretrained crop classification models for our catch crop classification, which, to the best of our knowledge, has not been attempted before. We addressed four key research questions:

1. What is the **accuracy gain of using pretrained deep learning models** in the classification of (winter) catch crops compared to a baseline model trained from scratch?
2. What is **the influence of the input period** on the performance of pretrained deep learning models, originally trained for main (summer) crop classification, when applied to (winter) catch crops?
3. What is **the effect of feeding an increasing number of training samples** to the pretrained model **during the (second) task-specific training stage**?
4. How well do the pretrained models, after an extra task-specific training stage, **perform on an unseen target year (temporal transferability)**?

Data

The ground truth labels for (task-specific) training and evaluation of the winter crop classification models were obtained through field visits. Three data sources were combined: (1) a dataset from the department of Agriculture and Fisheries of the Flemish government (winter years 2016-2021) obtained in the context of monitoring regional catch crop policy compliance, (2) a targeted field campaign from the winter year 2021 and (3) a targeted field campaign from the winter year 2022⁴. The original fine-class labels were grouped into seven broader categories: three catch crop groups (grass group, leafy group and mixtures) and four other groups (winter cereals, legumes, other crops and bare fields).

To download the Sentinel data, we applied the `query_gee.py` script from the Breizhcrops GitHub page⁵. We obtained the level 2A time series for all 12 bands, resampled to 20m resolution. This script retrieves all acquisitions available within a predefined temporal range, averaged over a specified geometry (parcel), including clouded acquisitions. Here, time series were downloaded between January and September the year after, spanning one year and nine months in total. Since the Breizhcrops models were trained on time series that included clouds (Rußwurm et al., 2020), we adopted the same approach. However, we decided to exclude images with more than 30% cloud cover to limit the noise from cloudy observations to some extent. Additionally, we interpolated the time series to equidistant 8-day composites, creating time series of exactly 45 timesteps in 12 bands, the required input dimensions for the pretrained models.

Methods

We used the Breizhcrops module in Python, which provides pretrained models for Sentinel-2 based time series crop classification (Rußwurm et al., 2020). These models were pretrained for main crop classification using a labeled dataset (610k labels) from the Brittany region in the North-East of France. Multiple models are available in the Breizhcrops module, including convolution- and recurrence-based methods, as well as the recently successful transformer models.

Four pretrained Breizhcrops models were compared: MSResNet⁶, TempCNN (Pelletier et al., 2019), LSTM (Rußwurm, Körner, 2017b) and Transformer (Rußwurm, Körner, 2019), which were implemented by Rußwurm et al. (2020). MSResNet and TempCNN are both convolution-based deep learning models, while LSTM is a recurrence-based deep learning model and the Transformer model incorporates both recurrent layers, and self-attention layers (Rußwurm et al., 2020). All these models have been successfully applied for land cover mapping or crop mapping. The pretrained models were compared with a baseline Random Forest (RF) model which is a widely used algorithm in crop classification that performed well for our data (see section 1). The RF model was trained from scratch and its

⁴ A winter year always spans from August of the indicated year until April the year after

⁵ BreizhCrops GitHub: <https://github.com/dl4sits/BreizhCrops>

⁶ <https://github.com/geekfeiw/Multi-Scale-1D-ResNet>

hyperparameters were tuned with a randomized search (Table 2.1). To adapt the pretrained models for our winter crop classification with seven classes, we replaced the last linear layer in each model with a linear layer consisting of seven output features instead of nine. All parameters of these pretrained models (not only the parameters of the final linear layer) were then fine-tuned in a task-specific training stage, over 10 epochs using the time series with ground-truth labels described in the Data paragraph above.

Table 2.1: Chosen hyperparameter values for the Random Forest (RF) algorithm.

	Parameter	Chosen value
RF	n_estimators	700
	max_depth	30
	max_features	None
	max_leaf_nodes	100

The four research questions were addressed through four separate experiments. In Experiment 1, we compared the performance of the different pretrained models. We used input time series spanning from January to December during the task-specific training stage and the model evaluation. This is the original range from the pretrained models, as they had been trained on main (summer) crop classification data. The training data used for this experiment is from the 2022 campaign year, 400 fields were used for training and 1354 for validation.

This temporal range might however not be the most optimal one for our application, a winter crop classification. Therefore, in Experiment 2, we used the same models and training/test parcels but shifted the input time series during task-specific training and evaluation by six months to July-June (Figure 2.1). This allowed us to assess the impact of optimizing the input period on classification performance. The same training and test data as for Experiment 1 were used.

Experiment 3 was designed to study the impact of the number of training samples used in the task-specific training stage on the classification accuracy. This was done using the July-June input period, with the training dataset size iteratively increased from 300 to 4000 samples. Training parcels were randomly selected, but stratified by catch crop type (see Vanpoucke et al. 2024 for full list). The training data used for this experiment is from the 2022 campaign year, the same set of validation (1354 fields) was used for validation across all sample sizes.

In Experiment 4, we tested the model transferability of all four models by training on data from 2018-2021 (using the July-June input period, 3850 fields) and testing on 2022. It should be noted that the validation set (1354 fields, 2022) remained constant across all experiments.

2022												2023					
Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June
Breizhcrops models																	
						Experiment											

Figure 2.1: Illustrating the shift of input time series for Experiment 2: the standard input time range of the Breizhcrops models indicated in gray, the input time range for the experiment in green.

In all four experiments, the classification models first classified the time series in the seven classification groups described in section 1, which were subsequently regrouped into three categories for the accuracy assessment: catch crops, other crops and bare field. The performance of the models was compared using the macro-averaged F1-score, as described in section 1. In addition to the F1-score, another metric to give an overall score to the classification is the Cohen’s kappa coefficient, or in short, kappa (Cohen, 1960). Kappa corrects for random chance agreements, which makes it useful in this context with class imbalance in the training data.

Results

Experiment 1 - Model comparison

The first experiment shows that the TempCNN model outperforms all other models, particularly in classifying the other crops and bare fields categories (Table 2.2). However, the reported kappa scores and F1 scores are quite low for all models. This could be due to the input period being January-December, which is not ideal since winter crops are typically present on the field starting in July-August-September. This hypothesis is tested in the next experiment. Another potential reason for the relatively low accuracies is the limited preprocessing applied to the time series. While this approach matches the preprocessing used to train the Breizhcrops models, it appears to be less effective in the context of our winter crop classification task.

Table 2.2: Kappa scores and (macro averaged) F1-scores presented by model type for experiment 1. Highest scores are indicated in bold.

	MSResNet	LSTM	TempCNN	Transformer	RF (baseline)
Kappa	0.25	0.07	0.39	0.02	0.06
F1					
Catch crops	93%	93%	93%	93%	93%
Other crops	34%	15%	50%	4%	12%
Bare fields	17%	0%	26%	0%	0%
Macro avg	48%	36%	56%	32%	48%

Experiment 2 - Influence of input period

From the results of the second experiment, we see that all models except LSTM benefit from a shift in the input period (Table 2.3). The Transformer model benefits most from the shift in input period, this improvement is more in line with the results found by Rußwurm et al. (2020), where the Transformer model outperformed all other models. Especially the classification accuracy of the groups other crops and bare fields seem to improve with the shift in the input period. This demonstrates that for the winter crop classification the input period July-June improves classification accuracy, even though the pretrained models were not trained on this period.

Table 2.3: Kappa scores and (macro averaged) F1-scores presented by model type for experiment 2. Highest scores are indicated in bold.

	MSResNet	LSTM	TempCNN	Transformer	RF (baseline)
Kappa	0.37	0.04	0.46	0.42	0.30
F1					
Catch crops	94%	93%	93%	94%	93%
Other crops	55%	6%	57%	57%	47%
Bare fields	19%	2%	35%	28%	10%
Macro avg	56%	33%	62%	60%	48%

Experiment 3 - Influence of dataset size

In the third experiment we tested the model accuracy when the models are trained on different training dataset sizes (Figure 2.2). Note that the validation set is kept constant, even though the training dataset changes in size (but not in composition). The results show that the performance of all models, except LSTM, improves as more training samples are used in the task-specific training stage. The pretrained Breizhcrops models (except LSTM) show the largest increase in accuracy as the training set increases. On a very small dataset (fewer than 500 training labels), the baseline RF model trained from scratch outperforms the pretrained models.

Figure 2.2: Macro-averaged F1 scores for five models across different dataset sizes: four fine-tuned pretrained models (MSResNet, TempCNN, LSTM, Transformer) and a baseline Random Forest (RF) trained from scratch.

Experiment 4 - Temporal model transferability

While all three previous experiments were executed using training data from the winter year 2022 only, for this last experiment the models were trained on the years 2018-2021 and then applied to an unseen target year 2022. Here we see that all models have a lower performance when evaluated on this unseen target year (Table 2.4). Except for the LSTM model, all models attain lower kappa scores and F1 scores compared to the second experiment. This experiment indicates that model transferability in catch crop classification remains challenging.

Table 2.4: Kappa scores and (macro averaged) F1-scores presented by model type for experiment 4. Highest scores are indicated in bold.

	MSResNet	LSTM	TempCNN	Transformer	RF (baseline)
Kappa	0.26	0.13	0.31	0.26	0.23
F1					
Catch crop	0.86	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.92
Other crop	0.40	0.17	0.47	0.40	0.45
Bare field	0.28	0.20	0.34	0.26	0.08
Macro avg	0.52	0.42	0.55	0.51	0.48

Conclusions

Our results show that pretrained TempCNN models outperform both the baseline RF and the other pretrained models (MSResNet, LSTM, and Transformer) tested in this section, for our application of winter crop classification. Still, the maximum kappa score achieved by these models is at best considered moderate on the scale of Landis and Koch (Landis & Koch, 1977). Important to note is that all models were trained with minimally preprocessed Sentinel-2 input time series that include a considerable amount of cloudy observations. This might explain, at least in part, the lower than anticipated accuracy values. Winter crop classification is likely more affected by the lack of cloud masking, as more cloudy circumstances are expected during most of their growing season. Also, our results suggest that transferability of models between years remains a challenge, even if with models retrained with labeled samples from multiple (winter) years. Most pretrained models (TempCNN, MSResNet, and Transformer) start to outperform the baseline RF model (trained from scratch) from as few as 500 dedicated (task-specific) training samples onward.

A disadvantage of using pretrained models is that the format of the task-specific input data must exactly match that of data they were pretrained with. The minimally preprocessed Sentinel-2 time series used in the Breizhcrops models seem to be less than ideal for our winter catch crop classification task. However, to the best of our knowledge, no alternative pretrained time series-based (crop) classification models were (publicly) available at the moment. Therefore, we advocate the development of foundation models for (satellite) time series-based crop (or general land cover) classification. Such pretrained models could then be fine-tuned for a wide range of downstream classification tasks through transfer learning (Ma et al., 2024). The pretrained transformer model for satellite-based time series classification, very recently developed by Tseng et al. (2024), is a first attempt at achieving this goal.

Section 3 - Data augmentation

Data augmentation, specifically with satellite time series as inputs, was implemented in use case 2 - Forest monitoring.

Introduction

The lack of large amounts of high-quality and balanced reference data is a persisting challenge for many remote sensing applications. When additional data collection is not possible, data augmentation has been put forward as a viable solution to increase the quantity, quality, and diversity of training samples (Mumuni & Mumuni, 2022; Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019). These data-related aspects can determine the performance of supervised machine learning, including deep learning algorithms. For the best results, training data should capture the task's key characteristics, enabling the model to learn informative patterns for all classes, reduce bias, and generalize reliably (Mumuni & Mumuni, 2022). Too few training samples may lead to model overfitting, a situation in which a trained model is overly adapted to the training data, and will perform poorly on unseen data. Data augmentation can also be used to address class imbalance. An imbalance dataset can lead to a predictive bias towards the class with the most samples, which is often not desirable.

At its core, data augmentation means creating extra training samples by adapting existing ones while keeping their original labels intact. This important requirement of preserving the labels is crucial for data augmentation to be effective (Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019). Data augmentation is a standard practice in image-based applications, including for some remote sensing tasks such as target recognition (Hao et al., 2023), picture enhancement (Lalitha and Latha, 2022), and change detection (Oubara et al., 2022). On the other hand, data augmentation of time series is not a common practice in remote sensing applications. However, it has been broadly applied in other disciplines that deal with pattern recognition (Iwana & Uchida, 2021). Data augmentation techniques can range from simple random transformations and pattern mixing to generative AI methods.

It is important to be aware that not all augmentation methods are appropriate for time series data. When working with temporal sequences, it is essential to preserve their time-dependent structure and to consider the physical meaning behind the measurements. Any synthetic variation must be realistic. For example, a flipped time series of a vegetation index representing a forest would not correspond with the natural progression of reflectance over time and misrepresent the biological processes involved. In short, methods to augment time series that represent spectral reflectance of vegetation should stay within the range of variations that vegetation naturally exhibits across space and time.

In this study, the focus is on the application of simple random transformation and pattern mixing on satellite image time series that represent different forest tree species in use case 2 - Forest monitoring . The overall and species-specific classification performance are evaluated.

Data

This study relies on reference and satellite data also used in the temporal model transferability study. A detailed description of the tree species labels derived from the Flemish forest inventory and the preprocessing steps for the Sentinel-2 time series can be found in this report in Section 1. On top of the five most common tree species that were investigated in that section, the analysis in this section includes three additional tree species, based on their relative abundance: beech, common alder, and Northern Red Oak.

Methods

Three classification methods were selected to assess the impact of time series data augmentation: Random Forest (RF), a 1-D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and a Long Short-Term Memory Fully Convolutional Network (LSTMFCN). The RF model was implemented with scikit-learn, while the CNN and LSTMFCN models were implemented using sktime.

Different groups of augmentation methods were tested, covering resampling methods, random transformation and pattern mixing. The most basic way to deal with data scarcity and imbalance is to resample the dataset. Random oversampling is a technique in which samples are simply duplicated. Strictly speaking, this is not a data augmentation technique as no new samples are generated, but it is added in this analysis as a second base for comparison, besides the non-augmented dataset. Next to random oversampling, three other resampling techniques were tested: SMOTE (Chawla et al., 2002), ADASYN (He et al., 2008) and GSMOTE (Fonesca & Bacae, 2023). These methods generate new samples based on a convex combination of existing samples. They were applied with the imbalance-learn package using standard parameters. The second group of tested augmentation techniques are simple random transformations. In this category, the first technique is jittering, which involves adding Gaussian noise to each time step of a time series, mimicking random noise that is added to the signal. The second technique involved temporally shifting the time series with one or more time steps to the left or the right. Such a transformation can mimic a temporal shift in phenology caused by a change in spatial regions, climate, or other environmental conditions. The third and final group of augmentation techniques involve pattern mixing, i.e., the creation of new samples by linearly combining two samples randomly selected from the same target class. This method aims to enrich the within-class variability while preserving class-specific temporal structure. Together, these methods provide a broad exploration of how different time series data augmentation strategies may influence model performance.

These methods were applied in two distinct ways regarding final class balance. In one setting, the existing class imbalance was kept intact. In the other setting, the augmentation methods were used to enforce class balance by increasing the class' sample size compared to the majority class sample size. At the same time, the total dataset size was varied with different augmentation factors, where a factor of k indicates that the final dataset contains k times as many samples as the original dataset. For example, a factor of 2 results in a dataset twice the size of the original, while a factor of 3 produces a dataset three times the

original size. The applied augmentation factors are: 1, 2, 10, 25, and 50. Overall classification performance was evaluated with the macro F1-score, while class-specific performance was evaluated with the class-specific F1-score.

Results

The applied data augmentation technique did not improve the performance of the RF model (Figure 3.1). In many cases, the augmentation had little effect or even reduced classification accuracy, with GSMOTE showing a consistently negative impact. This outcome suggests that RF does not inherently benefit from the applied data augmentations. Many augmented samples may fail to provide additional information that is useful and instead introduce noise or distort the underlying data distribution. Such redundancy can lead the decision trees to overfit or make poorer splits, yielding no performance gains or even degrading the overall model accuracy.

Figure 3.1: Weighted F1 scores (%) for different time series data augmentation methods implemented with different variations of dataset sizes (factors 1, 2, 10, 25, and 50) for the Random Forest (RF) algorithm for scenarios where dataset imbalance is kept intact (left) and balance is enforced (right). The red dotted line indicates the reference model performance based on the original (non-augmented) dataset.

For the CNN algorithm, data augmentation leads to clear improvements in model performance across different dataset sizes and in both scenarios of class balance (Figure 3.2). Similar to the RF results, however, GSMOTE severely degraded model performance in most cases relative to the non-augmented baseline. Since a 1D-CNN directly learns temporal patterns and local shape features through convolutional filters, it is expected that

augmented time series can meaningfully increase its exposure to valid temporal dimension and thereby improve generalisation. The applied augmentation methods effectively expand the space of valid temporal features the CNN can learn from. The model improvements lead to modest improvements in F1 scores for the black pine, beech, birch, and Northern red oak classes (not shown).

Figure 3.2: Weighted F1 scores (%) for different time series data augmentation methods implemented with different variations of dataset sizes (factors 1, 2, 10, 25, and 50) for the 1D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm for scenarios where dataset imbalance is kept intact (left) and balance is enforced (right). The red dotted line indicates the reference model performance based on the original (non-augmented) dataset.

The LSTMFCN model exhibits a higher baseline performance than RF and CNN, and data augmentation leads to modest improvements in many scenarios (Figure 3.3). As with the other models, GSMOTE consistently has a negative effect on model performance. The LSTMFCN model consists of two parts: a LSTM branch and a FCN branch. The LSTM branch processes the time series step by step to learn temporal dynamics such as long-range dependencies, trends and ordering relationships. The FCN branch applies 1D convolutions across the temporal dimension to learn local patterns and shape-based features, similar to a 1D CNN. Together, these branches enable the model to learn both global sequence structure and short-term temporal motifs. Because the tested augmentation methods introduce meaning variation at both of these scales, they help the model to generalise better and become more robust.

Figure 3.3: Weighted F1 scores (%) for different time series data augmentation methods implemented with different variations of dataset sizes (factors 1, 2, 10, 25, and 50) for the Long Short-Term Memory Fully Convolutional Network (LSTMFCN) algorithm for scenarios where dataset imbalance is kept intact (left) and balance is enforced (right). The red dotted line indicates the reference model performance based on the original (non-augmented) dataset.

GSMOTE consistently degraded model performance across all three classifiers. This suggests that its synthetic samples were not well aligned with the underlying temporal structure of the data. Although GSMOTE is an advancement over SMOTE, its core mechanism of generating new samples through geometric interpolation in feature space does not account for the ordered and highly structured nature of time series. As a result, the convex combination it produces can distort temporal trajectories and introduce unrealistic transitions between time steps. This provides proof for the idea that some augmentation techniques are not appropriate for vegetation time series if they do not consider the underlying biological patterns.

When comparing the remaining augmentation techniques, performance differences were relatively modest and showed limited differentiation. This suggests that these methods each introduce additional variation that increase the generalisability of the model, but their effects have an upper limit. A logical future research direction would be to apply a combination of augmentation techniques in one go rather than applying and evaluating each method in isolation. Different augmentation techniques target different aspects of temporal variation and may therefore have complementary effects when applied together.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the effectiveness of data augmentation for vegetation time series classification strongly depends on the choice of model and augmentation method. The RF method did not benefit from any of the applied augmentation techniques. Instead, several methods yielded no gain in model performance likely due to the model's inability to leverage temporal structure and its susceptibility to noise and redundant synthetic samples. In contrast, both deep learning models showed clear advantages from data augmentation. The 1D CNN in particular exhibited consistent performance gains across datasets sizes and class-balance scenarios. The LSTMFCN, which had the highest baseline performance out of the three algorithms, achieved modest improvements, supported by its dual capacity to learn both long-range dependencies and short-term local patterns.

Across all models, GSMOTE consistently degraded performance, underscoring the risks of applying vector-based oversampling methods to structured temporal data. Its geometric interpolation mechanism failed to preserve phenological trajectories, producing unrealistic samples that disrupt learning. Meanwhile, the remaining augmentation techniques provided relatively modest improvements, suggesting that they enhance model generalisability.

Overall, the results demonstrate the importance of carefully selecting augmentation strategies that respect the biological and temporal properties of vegetation time series. Future research should explore augmentation pipelines that combine multiple complementary techniques.

Section 4 - Semi-supervised learning

The use of semi-supervised learning was implemented in use case 8 - Water detection.

Introduction

The rationale of self-supervised learning is that a model can learn to extract meaningful representations from large amounts of unlabeled data. When the self-produced objective function is carefully designed, the model can capture high-level representations of the input data, and can be transferred to a supervised downstream task, thereby reducing the need for labeled samples (Wang et al., 2022). Thus, the self-supervised task is an unsupervised pre-processing step to be followed by a refinement to the specific task using labeled data. Several approaches to construct such self-supervised objective functions exist, including (1) generative methods, where the model learns to reconstruct or generate input data, (2) predictive methods, where the model learns to predict self-generated labels, and (3) contrastive methods, where the model learns to maximize the similarity between semantically identical inputs. A more detailed description of these approaches can be consulted in the review of Wang et al. (2022).

The concept of self-supervised learning has led to the conceptualization of so-called foundation models. These are big and generic models that have been trained on huge amounts of unlabeled data, and result in semantically meaningful features that can be used to train a variety of downstream applications using limited sets of truly labeled data. This field is evolving very rapidly, with Phritvi (Jakubik et al., 2023), Presto (Tseng et al., 2024), SatMAE (Cong et al., 2023) and SpectralGPT (Hong et al., 2024) being just a few examples that have been released recently.

As mentioned before, there generally is no lack of (unlabeled) remote sensing data. On the contrary, the exponentially increasing data volumes are posing challenges to the existing downlink and ground segment data storage capacity. On-board data processing and compression is an evident solution here, though generic lossless compression techniques only offer modest gains. Therefore “near-lossless” or lossy compression methods are gaining increasing attention. CORSA (Beusen et al., 2022) is a deep learning approach for near-lossless image compression that was first trained for Sentinel-2 RGB-NIR data and has been expanded to Sentinel-1 radar as well as EnMAP and PRISMA hyperspectral data (Beusen et al., 2023; Beusen et al., 2024). The framework exploits a VQVAE-like architecture (Vector Quantised-Variational AutoEncoder, see Figure 4.1) to generate a compact image representation containing deep feature vectors that are part of a codebook. These vectors can be represented by their codebook indices, which can be written to file as compact bit-arrays, suitable for downlinking. The full vectors are recreated afterwards from the indices using the same codebook, and the image can be reconstructed from the vectors using the decoder part of the model.

Figure 4.1: A visualization of the CORSA architecture.

Compression is an important but not the only application of the CORSA framework, as the deep feature vectors also have a semantic meaning. As such, CORSA can also be considered a foundation model. These features reduce the need for storage volume, due to the compression, and the need for labeled data, due to the increased level of information contained in the compressed features, creating a win-win situation. Therefore, the goal of this experiment is to investigate whether these features, obtained from Sentinel-2 RGB-NIR data, can serve as input to build a water detection algorithm, and how the latter compares to an end-to-end solution.

Data

The Flemish Institute for Nature and Forest Research (INBO) manages a dataset of natural closed water bodies, hence excluding industrial water surfaces and water courses, last updated in 2022 (Scheers et al., 2022). However, this is a static dataset that is updated in a spatially inconsistent way (i.e., not the full area is reconsidered for every update). In order to produce a ground truth of the highest possible quality for Sentinel-2 image segmentation, we have chosen to create manual annotations based on the aforementioned INBO database, but refining it with (1) topographic information, (2) high resolution aerial imagery acquired yearly in winter and 3-yearly in summer, and (3) visual interpretation of Sentinel-2 images.

This ground truth was generated for a selection of cloud-free acquisitions over seven Areas Of Interest (AOIs), shown in Figure 4.2. The period 2017-2021 was considered. For the test AOIs (in green), only Sentinel-2 images that were acquired within 24 hours from one of the available aerial images were considered. This ensures accurate annotations, but introduces a seasonal bias, as the aerial imagery is only acquired once or twice per year. For the training and validation AOIs, ten cloud-free S-2 images uniformly spread across the years were selected. Since the ground truth was refined with high-resolution imagery, some water bodies present in these datasets are invisible on the S-2 acquisitions, because they are covered by vegetation, too shallow or too small. In the dataset, these water bodies are

labeled as ‘difficult water’ and they were added to the ‘land’ (non-water) class for this particular application of semi-supervised learning.

In order to match CORSA’s input specifications, a set of 2100 patches of 120x120x4 pixels was selected for training and validation. The maximal overlap between patches was set to 80% and 90% of the patches were required to comprise at least 0.5% water pixels. The patches were split up into a training and validation set using an 80-20% random split.

Figure 4.2: Overview of the AOIs used for testing and training/validation respectively. The background is a Sentinel-2 false color composite (NIR-Red-Green).

Methods

The goal of this exercise is to perform a semantic segmentation on Sentinel-2 RGB-NIR data, discriminating between water and land. The benchmark end-to-end solution is U-Net architecture, trained on the uncompressed, raw Sentinel-2 RGB-NIR data.

To answer our research question, two types of networks taking CORSA representations as inputs were tested and compared to the end-to-end solution. The first type is called ‘Decoder + U-Net’, as it is equivalent to a pipeline consisting of a trainable CORSA decoder and a U-Net, as shown in Figure 4.3. Both the decoder and the U-Net are trained simultaneously as one network, which reflects a naive or straightforward approach to crafting a downstream algorithm with the aforementioned inputs.

The second type of network (shown in Figure 4.4) aims to leverage the underlying hierarchical structure of CORSA representations in addition to their semantic relevance. For this approach, the architectural possibilities are numerous and only two examples, chosen for their simplicity, were tested. Their structures are U-Net-like but contain separate ‘input blocks’, an ensemble of operations and layers, for different levels of representation. The two specific architectures are suggested in this study, respectively called ‘Crow-Net’ and ‘Shrike-Net’. They each use identical input blocks across their three levels, but the block type differs between both architectures. More specifically, Shrike-Net has one residual connection and extra layers compared to Crow-Net, resulting in a higher number of parameters (Table 4.1). They reflect a more sophisticated and flexible approach to the semi-supervised classification than the more simple ‘Decoder + U-Net’.

Figure 4.3: Architecture schematics for the 'Decoder + U-Net' network.

Figure 4.4: Architecture schematics blueprint for networks such as 'Crow-Net' and 'Shrike-Net'.

All three networks were trained with the same parameters and the same training data to enable fair comparisons. Power scaling was applied to the input data to match the distribution on which CORSA was trained, no data augmentations were applied. A decaying learning rate starting at 0.0001, early stopping and batch size of 128 were used during training.

For each network, the testing was performed as follows. Each test AOI was cut into overlapping patches. The output for these patches was predicted by the trained network and woven back together into the AOI by discarding the padding to minimize border effects. The final predicted image was sharpened with a threshold of 0.5, and anything above this threshold would be considered water. The ground truth was then compared to the aforementioned image using three metrics: the Jaccard score (also known as the Intersection over Union), precision and recall, all calculated for the water class. As for the training, the pixels belonging to the 'difficult water' class in the ground truth were considered as land. The scores obtained over the different test images and AOIs were then aggregated using area-based weights. Finally, the obtained scores are compared to the scores obtained using the benchmark end-to-end solution.

Results

To test whether CORSA deep features contain enough information to be used directly as input for a downstream water classification application, a combined 'Decoder + U-Net' and two more integrated CORSA-based architectures were trained and compared to an end-to-end U-Net. All networks were trained and evaluated using the same data. The resulting Jaccard, Precision and Recall scores for each model setup are listed in Table 4.1. As can be seen here, all setups have a similar performance, though minor differences exist. The algorithms that allow a separate encoding for different levels of representation

(Crow-Net and Shrike-Net) allow for considerably better performance, with Shrike-Net performing best. Adding separate pipelines for each level of representation induces extra parameters, however, which might explain partially the gain in accuracy.

Table 4.1: Result comparison between end-to-end U-Net and different CORSA-based algorithms. The shown metric values are aggregated over the 11 test images.

Algorithm	Metrics			# parameters)	Input type
	Jaccard	Precision	Recall		
End-to-end U-Net	70.2%	83.2%	82.1%	353 665	Original image
Decoder + U-Net	70.3%	81.6%	83.5%	1 212 165	CORSA representations
Crow-Net	71.4%	81.6%	85.2%	1 791 165	CORSA representations
Shrike-Net	72.2%	83.8%	83.8%	3 168 345	CORSA representations

To provide a more detailed insight into the results, the contingency map for model results based on the Sentinel-2 image of AOI2 acquired on April 1, 2019, are shown in Figure 4.5. As can be seen here, the main sources of confusion are narrow rivers and canals. These are missed mainly because of the limited resolution of Sentinel-2 compared to their width and the presence of nearby vegetation. A comparison of both maps indicates the slightly better performance of the Shrike-Net, with fewer false positives and especially fewer false negatives.

Figure 4.5: Contingency map for end-to-end U-Net (left) and Shrike-Net (right), showing false negatives (FN) in beige, true negatives (TN) in brown, true positives (TP) in dark blue and false positives (FP) in light blue.

Conclusions

This experiment was designed to test whether CORSA features can serve as input for a downstream application, in this case water detection. To do so, several CORSA-based architectures were trained, assessed and compared to an end-to-end solution. Results showed that the CORSA-based architectures even outperform the end-to-end solution.

These are very promising results, both regarding the compression aspect, as these results show that it is not needed to keep the original data to successfully build a downstream application – as well as the semi-supervised learning aspect – as these results show that the downstream application benefits from the feature embeddings that were obtained in a self-supervised way.

For this experiment, the same dataset was used for both the CORSA-based and the end-to-end setup. However, as the CORSA features contain higher level information compared to the original Sentinel-2 data, it is to be expected that the CORSA-based setup needs less annotated samples in order to converge and is more transferable to unseen regions. Both hypotheses will be tested in future work.

Section 5 - Active learning

Active learning was implemented in use case 5 - Catch crops

Introduction

The previous sections focused on approaches to circumvent the collection of extra labeled samples, by (1) reusing models trained for other time periods (section 1 - temporal transferability) or on other datasets entirely (section 2- transfer learning); (2) creating synthetic samples based on existing labels (section 3 - data augmentation) or leveraging the ability to learn from unlabeled samples (section 4 - semi-supervised learning). In this section on the other hand, we will go deeper into the possibility of collecting extra labels, but in the most efficient way. To this end, we will use the outcomes of (deep learning) models to help steer (new) data collection .

Active learning, also called optimal experimental design, is an approach designed to select the most informative or representative points in the unlabeled data space and recommends them for labeling (Cohn et al., 1994). It aims to achieve the maximum (gain in) accuracy using as few (new) labeled samples as possible, thus minimizing the cost of labeling and data gathering (Settles, 2008). Many active learning methods have been developed over the last decades, a particularly popular one is **uncertainty sampling**. This method selects those (unlabeled) sample locations where the model displays the highest uncertainty to gather extra (training) labels for (Li and Sethi, 2006). Uncertainty sampling was applied in use case 5 - Catch crops.

In this section, we aim to answer the following research questions:

1. How does uncertainty-based sampling, focusing data collection efforts on those parcels with the most uncertain (early-season) labels, impact the accuracy of end-of-season winter crop classification?

Data

The ground truth labels for (task-specific) training and evaluation of the winter crop classification models were obtained through field visits. Three data sources were combined: (1) a dataset from the department of Agriculture and Fisheries of the Flemish government (winter years 2016-2021) obtained in the context of monitoring regional catch crop policy compliance, (2) a targeted field campaign from the winter year 2021 and (3) an active learning-based field campaign from the winter year 2023⁷. In the latter field campaign, a selection was made with models trained on the first two data sources on time series ranging until the end of November. These models were applied to a selected set of fields, and the predicted labels with the highest uncertainty were selected for field visit. In total, 132 parcels were visited this way, 76 of which were used for active learning-based within-year training and the remaining 26 for testing. The original fine-class labels were grouped into seven

⁷ A winter year always spans from August of the indicated year until April the year after

broader categories: three catch crop groups (grass group, leafy group and mixtures) and four other groups (winter cereals, legumes, other crops and bare fields).

For all these fields, the openEO Python API was used for preprocessing and downloading dekadal (10-daily) NDVI time series from Sentinel-2 (TERRASCOPE_S2_TOC_V2) from August 1st until April 30th. Preprocessing steps included: (1) cloud masking with a kernel process (std dev 1.5, window size 11), (2) aggregation of time series to equidistant intervals (dekadal and monthly frequency) with the median (3) gap filling through linear interpolation, and (4) spatial aggregation over the field (catch crops).

Methods

An exploratory analysis was conducted using a Random Forest model with 400 trees. The model was trained on data collected from winter years 2016 to 2021 and subsequently applied to a test set of parcels from the winter year of 2023. Then, an active learning-like approach was tested where an identical Random Forest model was trained on the same dataset from 2016 to 2021, but with an additional 76 fields for which labels had been collected during the 2023 field campaign, where fields were selected based on uncertainty sampling. This updated model was then applied to the same 26-field test set from 2023. The classification results from both models on this test set were then compared in a qualitative way.

Results

Our results show that the overall accuracy slightly improves - from 58% to 65% - with the addition of 76 fields (1.7% of the whole training set) from the test year, for which the predictions based on models trained on previous years had a (very) high level of uncertainty (= uncertainty sampling) (Figure 5.5). Of the 26 fields used for testing, two fields from the leafy group are first misclassified as mixtures before the addition of extra training data; however they are correctly classified as leafy catch crops after adding this extra training data. Remarkably, fields from the grass group are almost always misclassified as winter cereal, probably due to the apparent absence of a downward trend like is present in the leafy catch crops group, which is most probably related to the removal of the catch crop of the field. During field work in winter, distinguishing between catch crops and winter cereals is also challenging; often, only revisiting the field later in the growing season would allow for clarification between the two groups, requiring additional field work.

Figure 5.5: Time series of the test set (26 fields) from the winter year 2023 : A) time series colored with ground truth labels, B) time series classified with the classification model trained with data ranging from the years 2016-2021 and C) time series classified with the model trained with 2016-2021 data and the 2023 data, collected through uncertainty sampling, a type of active learning.

Conclusions

The results of use case 5 show that active learning can be used to efficiently improve the quality of the training dataset, with a marked increase in model accuracy as the final outcome.

General conclusions

From the different experiments that have been conducted in the GEO.INFORMED project with respect to the optimization of reference data usage in deep learning and machine learning models, we can draw a number of general conclusions:

1. Deep learning models, even simple ones, suffer more from overfitting and poor transferability to unseen years than traditional machine learning methods. This is most likely due to their higher number of trainable parameters (section 1).
2. Multi-year training data markedly improves the **temporal transferability** of machine learning models for tree species classification to unseen years (section 1).
3. **Transfer learning** markedly improved the performance of deep learning models for (winter) crop classification, even outperforming traditional methods. From as few as 500 dedicated (task-specific) training samples onward, pretrained deep learning models start outperforming traditional machine learning methods trained from scratch (section 2).
4. **Data augmentation** is more advantageous for deep learning models than for their more shallow machine learning counterparts (section 3).
5. **Semi-supervised learning** with the CORSA, a near-lossless compression method as the unsupervised pre-training module, outperformed an end-to-end U-Net for inland water detection (section 4).
6. **Active learning** is a useful strategy for increasing the number of training samples for machine learning and deep learning methods in an efficient way (section 5).

Project outputs linked to this report

Heremans, S.; Somers, B.; Verhulst, M. 2023. Winter crop monitoring with ‘temporally-aware’ machine learning and deep learning methods. Presented at International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment (ISRSE). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18223623>

Ivashkovych, X., Landuyt, L., & Van Achteren, T. 2022. CORSA Deep Earth Observation Semantic Compression applied to Flood Detection. OBPDC Conference Athens, September 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18310356>

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